

Complex compounds of nickel, palladium and platinum involved in electron transfer processes

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New electron-transfer complexes of [M-N₂S₂] type formed by Ni^{II}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} with naphthoquinonic ligands have been synthesized. Sulfur and nitrogen atoms of the ligand are involved in the coordination to the metal. Their participation in the electron-transfer processes has been investigated by polarography.

The literature revealed new data related to the complex compounds formed by transition metals and ligands having conjugated double bonds¹. Most of these data deal with dithiol complexes. In these complexes electron delocalization processes occur and this makes the oxidation state of the metal-ligand bond order difficult to define. These complexes take part in one-electron redox reactions, giving rise to electron-transfer series : [M-S₄]²⁻ → [M-S₄]⁻ → [M-S₄]⁰. These combinations are planar irrespective of the oxidation state of the metal. As a consequence of the electron transfer, the following species can be obtained in this case :

where X = Y = S; X = Y = O; X = Y = N; X = O, Y = S; X = S, Y = N.

With the view of extending these investigations to the latter systems, in this work we have used naphthoquinonic ligands containing X = S, Y = N as donor atoms viz. 2-mercapto-3-(2-aminopyridin)-1,4-naphthoquinone (MAPNQ) and 2-amino-3-mercaptomethyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (AMMNQ).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes of Ni^{II}, Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} with naphthoquinonic ligands (MAPNQ and AMMNQ) were prepared by reported procedure². The complexes are microcrystalline coloured powders (Table 1). They are air-stable, insoluble in common organic solvents, sparingly soluble in dichloroethane and dioxane and soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulfoxide.

Table 1. Physical data of complexes*

Compd.	colour	M.p. °C	Mol. cond.** Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
[Ni(MAPNQ) ₂]	Red	136	2.50
[Pd(MAPNQ) ₂]	Brown	175	1.09
[Pt(MAPNQ) ₂]	Red	188	4.00
[Ni(AMMNQ) ₂]	Red	101	2.75
[Pd(AMMNQ) ₂]	Orange	138	1.22
[Pt(AMMNQ) ₂]	Brown	144	2.53

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

**In 10⁻⁴ M DMF solution, 22°.

Elemental analyses (Table 1) show that these complexes are of the type [ML₂], where M = Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II} and L = MAPNQ and AMMNQ.

The infrared spectra (Table 2) show important changes in the range 3500–3000 cm⁻¹ (NH₂). This shows that the nitrogen atom is directly involved in the coordination process. The intense bands in the 1600–1300 cm⁻¹ range (ν_{C-N}, coupling C-C and ν_{C-N}, coupling NH₂), appears in the complexes at slightly modified frequencies with diminished

Table 2. Characteristic IR frequencies (cm^{-1}) of ligands and complexes

Compd.	ν_{NH}	ν_{CO}	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ coupling C-C	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ coupling NH_2	ν_{CS}	$\nu_{\text{C=C}}^{\text{ske}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ plane def.	γ_{NH}	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$
MAPNQ	3380 3250	1670	1585	1360	1210	1100	1005	730	660
[Ni(MAPNQ) ₂]	3370 3280	1672	1580	1348	1250	1115	1020	750	665
[Pd(MAPNQ) ₂]	3250 3170	1670	1575	1350	1220	1110	1010	760	670
[Pt(MAPNQ) ₂]	3300 3100	1670	1578	1355	1230	1115	1010	740	678
AMMNQ	3442 3330	1670	1580	1350	1210	1150	1005	755	670
[Ni(AMMNQ) ₂]	3410 3310	1670	1585	1355	1278	1145	1005	758	678
[Pd(AMMNQ) ₂]	3420 3320	1670	1590	1358	1285	1148	1005	790	675
[Pt(AMMNQ) ₂]	3415 3325	1670	1585	1360	1283	1143	1005	756	673

intensities. An argument that supports the participation of the sulfur as a donor atom is the modification of the intense band at 1210 cm^{-1} , which expresses an important involvement of the C=S bond in the coordination (in the compounds they appear with a much lower intensity). Another argument is the modification in the $680\text{--}630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ band (C=S) which is changed in the complexes, with a much lower intensity. Hence, the IR spectral data indicate the participation of both the sulfur and nitrogen atoms in coordination to the metal.

The electronic spectral bands of the complexes (Table 3) were assigned according to the literature^{3,4}.

The molecular orbital approach was used to explain the structure of square-planar complexes of the d^8 elements. The metal orbitals involved in σ -bonding in square-planar complexes are the nd_{z^2} , $nd_{x^2-y^2}$, $(n+1)s$, $(n+1)p_x$ and $(n+1)p_y$. Nevertheless, judging from the values of the overlap integrals, $nd_{x^2-y^2}$, $(n+1)s$, $(n+1)p_x$ and $(n+1)p_y$ account for most of the σ -bonds, and nd_{z^2} makes only a minor contribution. The most important π -molecular orbital is formed by the $(n+1)p_z$ metal orbital and a combination of π -orbitals of the ligands.

The correlation of the bands observed in the electronic spectra for the studied complexes with those of $[\text{M}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$ [$\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Pd^{II} , Pt^{II}] prompted us to assume the following assignments (Table 3); ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$, ($d-d$); ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$, ($d-d$); ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$, ($d-d$); ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1u} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\sigma^*)]$, (C.T.); ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\sigma^*)]$, (C.T.);

Table 3. Electronic spectral data of the complexes

Compd.	$\lambda_{\text{max}} (\text{cm}^{-1})$	Assignment
[Ni(MAPNQ) ₂]	21973	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	29239	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	32468	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1u} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\sigma^*)]$
	38000	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\sigma^*)]$
[Pd(MAPNQ) ₂]	16700	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	21500	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	30500	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
[Pt(MAPNQ) ₂]	21800	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	26300	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	30300	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
[Ni(AMMNQ) ₂]	21200	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	29200	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	32600	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1u} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\sigma^*)]$
	37800	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_u [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{2u}(\sigma^*)]$
[Pd(AMMNQ) ₂]	16400	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	21400	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	30600	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
[Pt(AMMNQ) ₂]	21700	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	26500	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g} [b_{2g}(\pi^*) \rightarrow a_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$
	30400	${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g [e_g(\pi^*) \rightarrow b_{1g}(\sigma^*)]$

The relation between the bands in the present complexes and that described³ for the typical complexes $[\text{M}(\text{CN})_4]^{2-}$, leads to the conclusion that all the new compounds have the same square-planar geometry.

A quantummechanical interpretation of the absorption bands proper to the free and coordinated organic ligands gives informations about the coordination of the heteroatoms to the transition metal Ni^{II} ion⁵. The structural formu-

las of the free and coordinated organic ligands have been modeled on the computer. Their molecular geometry has been optimized using the Molecular Mechanics approach (MM⁺), the cartesian coordinates of the atoms being used to perform EHT calculation⁶. The computation was performed without iteration upon change and configuration, the results thus obtained are more reliable if the electronic transitions between MO levels are compared with the spectral ones.

In the complexes of Ni^{II} the first absorption band is assigned to an electron transfer from an electron lone-pair localized on the sulfur atom and the second one to an electron transfer from an electron lone-pair localized on the nitrogen atom. These transitions displaced toward higher wavenumbers for the coordinated ligands as a consequence of the coordination. The shifts are caused by the mixing of the antibonding states with *d*-metal orbitals as well as to the lowering of the electron lone-pairs energy that occurs after coordination. The last two bands are due to transitions between molecular orbitals practically localized on the oxygen atoms of naphthoquinone.

Comparison of the spectra of the complex compounds with that of the free ligands, shows that the first two bands shifted, while the last two ones did not shift, meaning that the oxygen atoms have nothing to do with the coordination, which is realised by means of the sulfur and nitrogen atoms of the ligands.

Strong ESR spectra were obtained for the nickel compounds. A [Ni-N₂S₂] type compound has a spectrum consisting of three components (Table 4). It is suggested that the first two components (*g*_{||}, *g*_⊥) originate in the splitting of the unpaired electron in the axial symmetry field of the complex, while the third is the result of the donor-acceptor type strong interaction between ligands and the central ion (*g*_i = 2.0022).

Table 4. ESR parameters

Compd.	<i>g</i> ₁	<i>g</i> ₂	<i>g</i> ₃	< <i>g</i> >	<i>g</i> _i	<i>A</i> _T gauss
	<i>g</i>	<i>g</i> _⊥				
[Ni(MAPNQ) ₂]	2.0058	2.0044	-	2.0049	2.0044	201.31
[Ni(AMMNQ) ₂]	2.0618	2.0175	-	2.0323	2.0022	97.90

The molar electrical conductivity data of complexes (Table 1) are in good agreement with that reported in literature for non-electrolyte bis-complexes, confirming the proposed formulation.

In the polarograms of the studied compounds there are three polarographic responses. This fact proves the existence, in solution, of several reduced species. It also proves that at the dropping mercury electrode the reduction of the

neutral and monoanionic species takes place according to the general reaction,

The other observed waves are due to the reduction of the ligands. The data show that, aside from participating in electron-transfer reactions, the evidenced species can also be obtained chemically, because the half-wave potential range from +0.95 to -0.95 V is a region in which oxidizing or reducing agents do not decompose the complex.

The study suggests that the complexes are of the type [M-N₂S₂], where M = Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}. This formulation is supported by the IR analysis, and which confirms that MAPNQ and AMMNQ act as bidentate ligands having both nitrogen and sulfur as donor atoms. The electronic spectra of these complexes lead to the conclusion that they are square-planar. Polarography data prove their involvement in the electron-transfer processes.

Experimental

Aqueous solutions (0.02 M) of NiCl₂·6H₂O (Merck, p.a.), PdCl₂ (B.D.H., p.a.), K₂[PtCl₄] (B.D.H., p.a.), and dimethylformamide solutions (0.02 M) of MAPNQ (recrystallized) and AMMNQ (recrystallized) were prepared.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-1600 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Unicam spectrophotometer. ESR spectra were recorded with an IFA Bucharest ART-5 spectrometer, working in the X-band (9060 MHz) and having a 100 kHz modulation of the magnetic field. The spectra were obtained at room temperature with a Mn^{II} standard (*g*₃ = 2.03584, *g*₄ = 1.98040, *H*₃ = 3179.5, *H*₄ = 3268.5). The polarograms were recorded with an Orion KTS 7-77-4/b instrument. The half-wave potentials of solutions (10⁻³ M) of complexes were measured at room temperature, using a calomel reference electrode and a dropping mercury electrode; a 0.1 M solution of tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate was used as supporting electrolyte. The electrical conductivity was measured on a Radelkis OK-102/1 conductivity meter, the cell constant being 0.897 cm⁻¹.

General procedure : [Ni(MAPNQ)₂] was obtained by adding dimethylformamide solution of ligand MAPNQ to aqueous solution of nickel chloride in a 2 : 1 molar ratio and set aside for 1 h. The resulting precipitate was washed with 96% ethanol, diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure. The other complexes were prepared using analogous methods.

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